

Evaluation of the Impact of Access to Training on Postharvest Loss Management Among Rice Farmers and Miller in Benue State

Azua Luper Luis, Innocent Otache Ogwuche, Terna Godfrey Ieren,

Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of post-harvest loss (PHL) management training access among rice farmers and millers in the region. A combination of quantitative and qualitative methods was applied, with data collected from 200 randomly selected rice farmers and mill workers. The binary logit model was utilized to estimate the impacts of access to PHL training on agricultural productivity and food security. The study found that only 40.5% of respondents had received training in PHL management, leading to significantly higher yields, greater knowledge in PHL reduction, and improved household food security. Farm size, group membership, access to credit, and rice production were positively correlated with training access, while family size, non-formal education, and distance to training centers were negatively correlated. Trained farmers adopted improved post-harvest practices, including better drying, storage, and pest control. Conversely, untrained farmers experienced higher post-harvest losses and lower productivity. Training access varied across regions, with rural farmers less likely to benefit. The study concludes that while PHL management training improves productivity and food security, access remains limited due to awareness, location, and cost. It recommends increased awareness, mobile training units, subsidized transport fees, and farmer group support to enhance training access. These interventions can improve PHL management, leading to better rice production and sustainable agriculture in Benue State.

Keywords

Post-harvest Loss, Access to Training, Food Security, Rice Farmers/Millers, Agricultural Productivity

1. Introduction

Rice is a fundamental staple crop, feeding over half more than 4.8 billion people across 176 countries, of the global population [21]. It is consumed by making it a crucial food source worldwide [18]. In

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terms of production, rice ranks as the second most important cereal globally, after wheat [22]. Nigeria stands out as the largest producer and consumer of rice in West Africa, yet domestic production struggles to meet demand, necessitating large-scale imports [8]. Nigeria produces approximately 5.4 million metric tonnes of rice annually, but its consumption nears 7 million metric tonnes, creating a supply gap that costs the country over \$4 billion annually in imports [20].

The Benue State region, regarded as the food basket of Nigeria, possesses vast agricultural potential due to its fertile soils and favorable climatic conditions. However, agricultural productivity, particularly in rice farming, remains hindered by post-harvest losses (PHLs). PHLs occur at multiple stages—threshing, milling, storage, and transportation—leading to significant economic losses [1, 13]. Studies indicate that threshing and milling alone account for nearly 60% of total losses, with some farmers reporting losses exceeding 40% of their total harvest [18].

A growing body of research emphasizes the critical role of post-harvest loss management (PHL) training in reducing losses [1,29]. Training enhances farmers' and mill workers' knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAPs) toward PHL management. Yet, little is known about the extent of training access, socio-demographic influences, and economic constraints affecting participation.

To bridge this gap, this study investigates PHL training access and its impact on rice farmers and mill workers in Benue State, Nigeria. It provides an in-depth analysis of barriers to participation, training effectiveness, and policy implications to improve rice production and ensure sustainable food security. Addressing these challenges through data-driven interventions is crucial for minimizing PHLs and enhancing Nigeria's agricultural sustainability.

1.2. Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study is aimed at evaluating the impact of access to training on post-harvest loss (PHL) management among rice farmers and rice mill workers in Benue State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study are:

- 1) To evaluate the frequency of farmers' and rice mill workers' access to post-harvest loss training,
- 2) To examine the socio-demographic and economic characteristics of rice farmers and rice mill workers with access to PHL training, and compare them with those who have not,
- 3) To assess the effect of access to PHL training on the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of rice farmers and rice mill workers regarding post-harvest loss management.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework guiding this study illustrates the causal relationships between access to post-harvest loss (PHL) management training and various influencing factors, categorized as farmer-related, farm-related, and institutional.

Farmer-related variables, such as family size, education level, gender of household head, marital status, and farming experience, are acknowledged to affect a farmer's decision to attend PHL training.

Farm-related characteristics, including farm size, farm location, and rice yield, also influence training access, often through resource availability and logistical constraints [26].

Institutional factors, particularly membership in farmer groups or cooperatives, are noted to enhance access through improved information flow and support networks.

The framework assumes that perceived benefits of training are central to farmers' decision-making regarding participation.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

A multi-theoretical lens informs the study. The Entropy Theory [30] conceptualizes the natural degradation of agricultural produce post-harvest without intervention, emphasizing the need for training in preservation techniques. Systems Theory [31] views PHL through the interdependent components of the agricultural supply chain, where

weaknesses in one part (e.g., storage) affect the whole system. Human Capital Theory [15] underscores the value of training in increasing the productivity of farmers and mill workers. The Behavioral Change Model [7] highlights that attitudes, perceived control, and social norms influence adoption of post-harvest practices. Lastly, the Economic Loss Theory [19] positions PHL reduction as a strategy to minimize economic inefficiencies and enhance farmers' income.

These theories collectively provide a robust foundation for evaluating how knowledge, systemic factors, behavior, and institutional dynamics influence access to and the effectiveness of PHL training.

2.3. Empirical Evidence

Studies from across Sub-Saharan Africa highlight the significant role that training plays in reducing post-harvest losses and improving food security [24].

Socio-economic characteristics such as education, farming experience, household size, access to credit, and cooperative membership have consistently been found to affect farmers' access to agricultural training [2, 11, 3].

Empirical research in Uganda [25] and Nigeria [28] further reinforces the impact of farm size, training location, and household dynamics.

Moreover, economic studies demonstrate that reducing PHLs directly correlates with increased farm

income and improved household food security [16, 4].

2.4. Methodological Approaches

A review of existing studies reveals that most assessments of training access employ Binary Logistic Regression (BLR) or Probit models, coding training exposure as a binary variable (1 = access, 0 = no access).

These models enable the identification of key socio-economic predictors such as gender, age, education level, and household size [3, 12, 25].

BLR is favored due to its predictive capacity and simplicity in modeling binary outcomes.

This study adopts the BLR model to analyze training access among rice farmers and mill workers in Benue State, Nigeria, aiming to provide robust empirical insights for policy and intervention development.

3. Methodology

3.1. Introduction

The methodology section deals with the research

design, approaches to data collection, the sample selection process, and statistical analysis techniques used to assess access to training on post-harvest loss management among rice farmers and mill workers in Benue State.

3.2. Research Design

This study uses a cross-sectional survey design in evaluating the access to training on post-harvest loss management among rice farmers and mill workers in Benue State — analyzed using binary logistic regression. Data were collected once from a sample representing the population of rice farmers and mill workers in the state.

3.3. Study Area

This research was conducted in Benue State, Nigeria, which is one of the highest rice-producing areas. In this regard, the study considered the major rice-producing local governments (LGAs) in the state for a thorough representation. From Zone A, Kwande and Vandeikya LGAs were considered, while from Zone B, Makurdi and Buruku LGAs were selected.

Figure 1. The Geographic location of the study area.

3.4. Population and Sampling

Population: The target population comprised all rice farmers in Benue State.

Sampling Technique: A multi-stage sampling technique was employed:

Stage 1: Selection of LGAs: Purposeful selection of LGAs based on the intensity of rice farming.

Stage 2: Selection of Communities: Random sampling of communities within the selected LGAs.

Stage 3: Selection of Farmers: Random sampling

of rice farmers within the selected communities.

Sample Size Determination: The sample size was determined using Cochran’s formula for sample size calculation for categorical data. Assuming a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%, the initial sample size was calculated and adjusted for the population size [18].

3.5. Data Collection

Data Collection Instruments: Structured questionnaires were used to collect data. The

questionnaire was divided into sections covering:

- a) Demographic information (characteristics) (age, gender, marital status, education, occupation, etc.).
- b) Access to training on post-harvest loss management.
- c) Factors influencing access to training (e.g., distance to training centers, membership in farmer groups, access to information, etc.).
- d) Knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) regarding post-harvest management, etc.

Pre-testing: The questionnaire was pre-tested on a small sample of rice farmers and rice mill workers in a similar setting to ensure clarity and reliability. Necessary adjustments were made based on the feedback from the pre-test. Furthermore, the questionnaire was validated by professional statisticians, Dr. David Kuhe and Prof. M. Imande.

Data Collection Procedure: Enumerators were trained and administered the questionnaires to conduct face-to-face interviews to 200 randomly selected farmers and rice mill workers from the selected local governments (Kwande, and Vandeikya) from Zone A, (Buruku, and Makurdi) from Zone B. The data collection process was supervised to ensure consistency and accuracy. Collected data was subjected to analysis using SPSS version 26 software and MS Excel version 16.

Note: data is available on request @azualuisl@gmail.com

3.6. Methods of Analysis

3.6.1. Statistical Analysis

The binary logistic regression analysis was the predominant statistical approach to find the factors affecting post-harvest management losses among rice. In the analysis, the dependent variable is access to training (Yes/No).

3.6.2. Binary Logistic Model

Binary logistic regression models are particularly handy in analyzing a dataset in which one or more independent variables are likely to be influential to some outcome. This outcome is captured as a dichotomous variable, taking only one of two possible values. A binary regression model attempts to find the best-fitting relationship between dependent and independent variables. For that purpose, it estimates model parameters to predict a logit transformation of the probability of the outcome of interest.

$$\text{logit}(p) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_k X_k \quad (1)$$

It follows from equation (1) that

$$p = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_k X_k)}} \quad (2)$$

Where p is the probability of the presence of the characteristic of interest, the β_i 's and the X_i 's, $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ are the regression coefficient and the independent variables respectively. The logit transformation is defined as the logged odds, where;

$$Odds = \frac{p}{1-p} =$$

$$\frac{\text{probability of the presence of the characteristic}}{\text{probability of the absence of the characteristic}} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\text{logit}(p) = \ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) \quad (4)$$

Logistic regression is a model that estimates its parameters by maximizing the likelihood of observing the given sample data, as opposed to standard regression, which estimates its parameters by minimizing the sum of squared error. The forward Wald stepwise (Likelihood Ratio) regression method is used for building the model.

For this work, the logistic regression model would be specified as follows:

A comparative analysis was done to distinguish between farmers and rice mill workers with and without access to post-harvest loss (PHL) management training. Continuous variables were analyzed using T-tests, while categorical variables were analyzed with Chi-square tests as described by [5]. Meanwhile, Descriptive statistics were also used to assess the number of PHL management practices adopted by farmers and rice mill workers. The dependent variable of this study is a dichotomous variable assigned 1 for access to PHL management training and 0 for no access. This classification assumes that among the farmers, those who realize the usefulness of the training are more likely to

participate [6,11, 27] The relation of the binary dependent variable with the independent variables was studied using Binary logistic regression. Its choice over Probit models is attributed to the ease of computation and more intuitive interpretation [6] Past studies established usefulness of Binary logit methods in the agricultural sector [9, 14, 10, 17, 23].

The likelihood of whether a farmer or rice mill worker has received training on post-harvest loss (PHL) management has been defined in Equation 5 as attributed to the work of Jaza et al. (2018).

$$\Pr(Y = 1) = \left[\sum_{k=1}^k \beta_k X_k \right] \quad (5)$$

Arya et al. (2020) stated the probability of having no access to PHL training in his research, which is expressed in equation 6 ;

$$\Pr(Y = 0) = \left[\sum_{k=1}^k \beta_k X_k \right] \quad (6)$$

Similarly, Endalew and Yenewa (2021) and Jegede (2020) stated the binary logistic regression in their research as presented in Equation 7.

$$\text{Logit}(p) = \ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_i \times_i + U_i. \quad (7)$$

In Equation 7 above, P indicates the probability of having access to PHL management training. β_0 is the constant term, while β_1 denotes the regression coefficient, which will be obtained from the regression results. Finally, U_i represents the error term.

Table 1 presents the variables used in the analysis of factors influencing access to Post-Harvest Loss (PHL) training. The dependent (explained) variable is "Access to PHL training," which is measured as a binary variable, where 1 indicates access and 0 indicates no access. This variable is plotted along the Y-axis, as it is the outcome being explained by other

variables.

The explanatory (independent) variables, which are plotted along the X-axis, consist of both continuous and binary types. These variables aim to capture the socioeconomic and demographic characteristics that may influence a household's likelihood of accessing PHL training.

Table 1. Explained and explanatory variables.

Explained variable	Measurement	Variable type	Sign Expectation
Access to PHL training	1—Yes,0—No	Binary	—
Explanatory variables			
Household size	Individual(s) per household	Continuous	±
Education	1—Formal,0—non-formal	Binary	±
Farming/Milling experience	Years in farming and milling	Continuous	±
Farm size	Acres	Continuous	±
Locality Status	1—Rural,0—Urban	Binary	±
Group membership	1—Member,0—No	Binary	+
Rice Yield	In Kilograms	Continuous	±
Gender of the Household head	1—Male,0—Female	Binary	+
Marital Status	1—Married,0—Unmarried	Binary	+
Distance to training centers	Kilometers covered	Continuous	±

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Rice Farmers and Rice Mill Workers with Access to Training on PHLs Management

Figure 3 presents the outcome of the quantity of farmers and mill workers who experienced frequent or rare access to PHL management training. A total of 81 (40.5%) of the 200 sampled respondents received PHL management training. Analysis further reveals that 38 (46.9%) of the trained respondents had access to training on a frequent basis, while 42 (51.9%) were trained on a rare basis. With regard to sponsorship, 31 (38.3%) were sponsored, and 50 (61.7%) self-sponsored or had NGO/private sector support.

The remaining 119 (59.5%) received no training whatsoever and operated on a trial-and-error basis. This underlines the need to train farmers and mill workers in modern agricultural methods to enhance farm production and milling accuracy.

Table 2 below shows the sources of information for farmers and mill workers who received PHL management training. The primary sources of information were: Farmers' association (40%), Radio/television broadcast (26%), Extension workers (22%), social media (17%).

These findings suggest that while farmer groups and the mainstream media channels succeed in disseminating information, social media can be optimized to further enhance training and extension activities among farmers and rice mill workers.

Figure 2. The Frequency of farmers with access to PHLs management trainings.

Table 2. Information Sources for PHL Training.

Sources	Number of farmers(f)	Percentage (%)
Farmers Association	40	40
Extension workers	10	26
Radio/Television Broadcast.	26	22
Social media	14	17

4.2. Comparison of Farmers and Mill Workers Based on Access to PHL Management Training

Aside-by-side comparison of rice farmers and mill workers who received PHL training versus those who didn't shows some striking differences in productivity and access to resources. The trained

farmers boasted significantly higher yields ($P < 0.01$) and larger plots of land ($P < 0.01$), hinting at a clear connection between training and better agricultural output. They also had more years of formal education ($P < 0.01$), were generally older ($P < 0.01$), and had more farming experience ($P < 0.01$), suggesting that both education and experience play a big role in adopting improved farming techniques. Institutional factors were also important, as the trained farmers enjoyed better access to credit ($P < 0.05$), likely thanks to the skills they picked up during their training. Moreover, these farmers reported greater household food security ($P < 0.05$), which shows that PHL management training really helps with food availability. Lastly, the study highlighted that untrained farmers and mill workers faced significantly higher post-harvest losses ($P < 0.01$) compared to their trained counterparts. These results emphasize just how vital PHL management training is for boosting agricultural productivity, improving financial access, enhancing food security, and cutting down on post-harvest losses.

Table 3. Comparison of Access to PHL Trainings Across Farmers' and Millers' Socio-Demographics.

Variables	Measurement	HasAccess	HasNoAccess	Overall Mean ± SD	P-Value
RiceYield	kg/Acre	1,494.00	790	296.7±374.60	0.010
Farmsize	Acres	6.33	3.24	6.15±2.50	0.012

Variables	Measurement	HasAccess	HasNoAccess	Overall Mean ± SD	P-Value
Education	Years	8.85	7.32	6.66±1.25	0.004
Age	Number	40.64	46.30	45.01±12.85	0.003
Experience	Years	16.67	22.13	20.89±11.90	0.002
Accesstocredit	yes,otherwise	0.98	0.86	0.89±0.30	0.015
Access to extension	yes, otherwise	0.96	0.98	0.98±0.14	0.35
Food secure	yes, otherwise	0.5	0.24	0.42±0.12	0.038
Reported PHLs	yes, otherwise	0.2	0.86	0.60±0.24	0.000

4.3. Effect of Access to PHL Training on KAP of Rice Farmers and Rice Mill Workers Regarding PHL Management

This study shines a light on how post-harvest loss (PHL) training can significantly boost the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of rice farmers and mill workers when it comes to managing PHL. The training programs have proven effective in raising awareness about the right ways to harvest, handle, and store rice, which ultimately helps improve food security and farmers' incomes. According to survey results, 81 out of 200 respondents had undergone PHL training, and those who did showed a much better understanding of proper drying techniques, 79 out of 124 respondents, to be exact.

Moreover, the training had a positive effect on attitudes; 175 respondents considered PHL management to be "important," and an impressive 98% of those who were trained found the sessions beneficial. The training also led to the adoption of innovative techniques for reducing PHL, such as using hermetic storage bags and solar dryers, along with better utilization of storage facilities and regular checks on rice for any damage. In summary, these findings are consistent with earlier research, reinforcing the idea that greater access to PHL training not only enhances knowledge and attitudes but also improves practices, ultimately leading to lower post-harvest losses and more efficient rice production.

4.4. PHL Management Practices Adopted by the

Farmers

This study looked into how rice farmers and mill workers manage post-harvest losses (PHL). It focused on how well they adopt essential practices like harvesting, drying, sorting, packaging, transporting, and marketing their rice. The research also explored the use of chemical treatments for pest and disease control before storing the rice. The findings showed that while 70% of the participants harvested their rice on time, only 44% took the necessary steps to properly dry their grains, which puts most of them at risk of spoilage. Packaging was done by just 20% of the respondents, primarily mill workers, and only 13.5% used chemical treatments. Transportation and marketing were noteworthy, with 65% of the respondents getting their rice to market and 60% selling their produce. The study points out significant gaps in PHL management, especially in drying, packaging, and pest control, and suggests that focused training and capacity building could really boost post-harvest efficiency and cut down on losses.

Table 4. PHL Management practice adopted by the farmers and Rice Mill Workers.

Practices	Quantity of Rice Farmers/	Percentages %
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	Millworkers	
Harvesting in Time	140	70
Drying	88	44
Sorting	47	23.5
Packaging	40	20
Application of Chemicals Before storage	27	13.5
Transporting from the Farm to the store	200	100
Transporting from the Store to the market	130	65
Marketing	120	60

4.5. Constraints Preventing Access to PHL Management Training

Farmers identified two key issues that prevented them from accessing PHL training (Figure 3). The most recurring reason cited was that they lacked information about the existence of training. They further stated that the training centers were far from their communities, and thus it was difficult to access due to the elevated cost of transportation.

Figure 3. Constraints preventing access to PHL management training.

4.6. Impact of Access to Training on PHLs Management

This study uses a binary logit model to explore how access to post-harvest loss (PHL) management training affects rice farmers and mill workers. The model shows a strong fit (pseudo- $R^2 = 39.50$) and is statistically significant ($P < 0.01$), pointing out the key factors that influence access to training. The results reveal that factors like farm size, rice yield, and group membership significantly boost the chances of accessing training, highlighting the importance of commercial focus and working together. On the flip side, having a larger family size tends to

reduce access, likely because of competing household responsibilities. Interestingly, marital status plays a positive role in training participation, with married individuals being 11.5% more likely to take part in training. The distance to training centers also turned out to be a crucial factor, with noticeable regional differences—in Kwande/Vandeikya were 22% less likely to access training compared to those in Makurdi/Buruku, which points to some infrastructural challenges. In summary, the study emphasizes the need to tackle socio-economic and geographical obstacles to improve access to PHL management training.

Table 5. Binary Estimates of the evaluation of impact access to PHL Training.

Variable	Regression Coefficients	Error Margin	Incremental Impact
Family Size (Head count)	-0.884	0.413	-0.08
Education	0.115	0.402	0.010
Farming experience	0.539	0.381	0.048
Farm size	0.819	0.452	0.074
Farm location (Study areas)	-4.842	0.765	0.559
Group membership	1.278	0.459	0.119
Rice Yield	0.132	0.077	0.127
Gender of the household	0.306	0.531	0.011
Head			
Marital status (Married)	1.237	0.515	0.109
Distance to training Center	-1.423	0.630	0.110
Constant	-2.556	1.610	----

p-value = 0.000, LRCh2=101.50, Pseudo R² =0.375, N = 200,1,5,10% level significance

5.1. Conclusion

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

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Statistics indicate that significant post-harvest losses (PHLs) in rice production are prevalent when farmers lack training and employ trial-and-error methods, which suggests that farmers unwittingly might be causing these losses. The majority of smallholder farmers are also not skilled at managing PHLs, which explains why targeted training and demonstration are important. In a bid to fill this knowledge gap, this study examines the determinants of smallholder rice farmers' access to PHL management training in Benue State, Nigeria.

A survey of 200 randomly selected rice farmers was conducted, and then binary logit analysis was performed. The findings were that few farmers received training on PHL management, but among those who did, there were improvements in household food security and farm output. The analysis showed significant determinants of training access, including family size, farm size, access to credit, group membership, rice yield, marital status, and distance from training centers.

The research concludes that access to training in PHL management is negligible for rice farmers and mill workers of Benue State, where lack of exposure and distant-to-reach training centers are the greatest obstacles. It also discovered that farm size, belonging to a group, greater quantities of rice produced, and marital status increased access to training, but farm size, distance to training centers, and larger household sizes reduced access.

5.2. Policy Recommendation

A number of primary policy interventions are suggested to enhance the availability of post-harvest loss (PHL) management training for rice in Benue State, Nigeria. They include:

- 1) **Awareness Creation:** It's essential for government bodies, agricultural organizations, and local media to team up and boost awareness about the PHL management training available. They can do this through radio, TV, and social media platforms.
- 2) **Accessibility of Training Locations:** We should think about introducing mobile training vans or setting up community-based training centers to reach farmers who are in remote areas.
- 3) **Flexible Training Schedules:** Training sessions need to be scheduled at times that work well for farmers, fitting into their daily routines.
- 4) **Subsidized Transportation:** The government should lend a hand to farmers, particularly those in hard-to-reach areas, by covering some of their transportation costs to training sessions.
- 5) **Strengthening Farmer Groups and Cooperatives:** Policies should encourage the formation and sustainability of farmer groups, which can

help improve access to training and facilitate resource sharing.

- 6) Customized Training Programs: Training should be tailored to meet the needs of different types of farmers, offering cost-effective solutions for smallholders while providing advanced technology training for larger-scale farmers.
- 7) Technology Integration: We can make use of mobile phones and the internet for remote learning, utilizing webinars, instructional videos, and online forums.
- 8) Credit Access for PHL Management: It's important to link PHL training with credit programs, allowing farmers to invest in better post-harvest management practices.
- 9) Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) System: Establishing a system to evaluate the effectiveness of training programs is crucial, ensuring we continuously improve based on feedback from farmers.
- 10) Gender Inclusivity: Training programs should be designed to be inclusive for both men and women, addressing specific barriers like time flexibility and equal access to resources.

Abbreviations

PHL Post Harvest Loss

KAP Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices

Author Contributions

Azua Luper Luis: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft

Innocent Otache Ogwuche: Supervision, Validation

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Biography

Azua Luper Luis is a Nigerian born on June 20, 1994. He began his education at NKST Primary School Bebe, earning his First School Leaving Certificate as the best graduating student. He later attended St. Andrews Secondary School, Adikpo (SASSA), where he obtained both the West African Senior School Certificate and the National Examination Council Certificate in 2013. Luis pursued a Bachelor's degree in Computer Engineering at ISCOM University, Benin Republic, graduating in 2018 as the best graduating student. He is currently undertaking a Master of Science in Biostatistics in the department of mathematics and computer science at the Centre for Food and Research Technology, Benue State University (2023–2025). He is the founder of an ICT center, where he trains students in research and data analysis, and provides consultancy services in technology and data science.